

Computer Vision-Based Volleyball Analytics

NH Wanigasingha^{1,2#}, MKA Ariyaratne¹, and RM Silva³

¹Department of Computer Science, Faculty of Applied Sciences, University of Sri Jayewardenepura, Sri Lanka.

²Faculty of Graduate Studies, University of Sri Jayewardenepura, Sri Lanka.

³Department of Statistics, Faculty of Applied Sciences, University of Sri Jayewardenepura, Sri Lanka.

#hirushanethni@sjp.ac.lk

Abstract – The field of sports analytics is being revolutionized by computer technology that can "see" and understand videos. This research proposes an integrated analytical framework for enhancing volleyball strategy, addressing the limitations of traditional observation-based analysis in this fast-paced, complex team sport. The study involves three main phases: first, conducting a comprehensive review to identify the state-of-the-art technologies in volleyball video analytics and identify gaps in object detection, tracking, and strategic frameworks; second, develop a specialized multi-angle volleyball video dataset with detailed, synchronized annotations of player movements, ball trajectories, and tactical events; and third, creating the core framework that combines computer vision for precise tracking, Bayesian analytics for probabilistic reasoning and uncertainty quantification, and optimization methods to simulate scenarios and identify optimal serving, attacking, and rotation strategies. The final system aims to translate raw tracking data into actionable insights, providing coaches and analysts with a sophisticated decision-support tool to improve tactical planning and overall team performance. The effectiveness of the framework will be validated on real-world game data using metrics such as Precision, Recall, F1 Score, and ROC Curve & AUC.

Keywords: Object detection, Object tracking, Sports Analytics, Volleyball, Computer Vision